

CYNARA SCOLYMUS L. EXTRACT FROM THE BEGINNING OF THE PLANT IN VITRO ANTI-CANCER ACTIVITIES

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Today, the number of cases with diseases that are life-threatening, with a high mortality rate is increasing[1]. One such dangerous disease is cancer. There are many SAPS to the ever-increasing incidence of this disorder among humans. Currently, women have a very high incidence of types such as pancreatic cancer, cervical cancer [2]. The basis for this can also be seen the absence of ordinary sex life, an increase in the number of deductions, a large number of products from the environment and food abandonment. Since the decision on many treatment measures for cancer, there have not yet been found drugs that fully treat this disease [3]. We ham in our research work *Cynara scolymus* L. we analyzed biological activities in vitro against several types of carcinogenicity of extracts from the root of the plant. To do this, an extract in chloroform, ethylacetate hamdail alcohol from the leaves of the plant was studied for its biological activity in relation to cancer cells such as uterine boy cervical adenocarcinoma HeLa, folk carcinoma Hep-2 and blue cancer HBL-100. The purpose of the evaluation on the extract against healthy cells in the process of communication is the use of fibroblasts obtained by biopsy from the skin of newborn rats. To assess the biological activity of extracts, the quality of conversational control has been used cisplatin drugs, which are widely used against cancer today. The extract from the analysis process was obtained at a concentration of 100 mcg / ml, and from cancer cells at a concentration of 2×10^4 .

The result was found to be 44.7% ethanol extract, the highest thinning causative agent for uterine maintenance adenocarcinoma, according to the tested extract. No boological activity was recorded in ethylacetate and chloroform extracts. In the case of cisplatin, where the interview was taken as a control, the ingestion rate was 86.5%. The highest activity compared to folk carcinoma Hep - 2 was when ethylacetate extract was observed and its ingestion value was 36%. In contrast to Lake cancer and T-lymphoblastic library cells, an almost effective definition is observed in ecstreacts. Currently, Research is ongoing on the extraction of secondary metabolite repair by these techniques and their study of anticancer effects.

Literature:

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